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HOW TO DEAL WITH PROFESSIONAL BURNOUT IN MEDICAL TEACHERS

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Abstract

Professional burnout of teachers is a very common and urgent problem of higher medical school. Mental health problems, manifestations of emotional burnout directly affect the health of teachers, their psycho-emotional state and professional qualities. The article provides a theoretical analysis of the causes, factors, forms and levels of professional burnout of teachers, outlines ways and means of diagnosis. The negative impact of burnout on the mental health of the individual, its formation and further professional development is substantiated and methods for preventing the development of this pathology are substantiated.

Key words: professional burnout, syndrome, education, mental health, stress, well-being.

The history of the term "emotional burnout" begins in the XVII century. when the Dutch surgeon Nicolaes Tulp said "shining on others, I burn myself", and in 1974 the American psychiatrist H. J. Freudenberger first drew attention to this phenomenon and described it as "defeat, exhaustion or wear and tear that occurs to humans due to sharply increased demands on own resources and forces ". The term "professional burnout" appeared in the psychology literature in 1974 to describe the mental state of healthy people who interact intensively with patients, clients and are constantly in an emotionally charged atmosphere during professional care. Currently, this term has the diagnostic status "Z 73.0 Burnout, state of life exhaustion" in the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems 10th Revision (ICD-10) -2015 -WHO Version for; 2015).

Occupational burnout is a condition of emotional, physical and mental exhaustion caused by chronic stress. This condition most often occurs among professionals who work in close contact with people and are forced to communicate a lot with others. This group includes teachers [1]. Given the current: drastic reform

changes in the structures of educational institutions, which are taking place against the background of the socio-economic crisis, associated not only with market relations in education, but also with the beginning of the Covid-19 pandemic. Over the last two years, burnout has taken on a different form, with signs of isolation, fears for the lives and health of relatives, and distance learning. The transition to distance learning has created new challenges for teachers. We had to quickly master new forms and approaches to teaching. "Quarantine" factors influencing the development of burnout are divided into two groups: organizational and psychological - factors related to the new special organization of work in quarantine; psychological - factors associated with new psychological features of professional activity and their own subjective characteristics. Working in such a rhythm is extremely difficult to maintain your mental health and prevent emotional burnout.

There are the following main factors that play an important role in the formation of emotional burnout:

✓ personal - dissatisfaction with professional growth, lack of motivation at work, low wages;

✓ role - lack of clear or uneven responsibility for their professional responsibilities and integration for a successful end result;

✓ organizational - intensive communication, the presence of conflicts with colleagues and lack of support from the management of the institution.

One of the main reasons for the development of this syndrome is psychological and mental fatigue, which leads to imbalance as a result of prolonged occupational stress. American psychologists C. Maslach and C. Jackson, who have been conducting research on this subject since the 1980s, have suggested that the syndrome is a three-component system: depletion, depersonalization, and self-reduction. personal aspirations.

Workaholism (Karoshi syndrome) - which stands for "wear and tear work that leads to premature death." To date, about 30,000 workers worldwide have become legally confirmed victims of this insidious syndrome.

Who should stop and change the approach to the distribution of their working time?:

✓ those who continue on their own initiative a working week over 40 hours;

✓ those who perform part of the work in bed, during illness, on weekends or on vacation;

✓ for those who are convinced that a lot of work is a manifestation of respect and love for the profession and devotion to the profession

✓ those who think about working behind the wheel of a car or at bedtime.

Burnout syndrome manifests itself in symptoms that may often go unnoticed for a long time, but experts combine them into the following groups of symptoms and encourage you to ignore the appearance:

- emotional exhaustion;
- mental exhaustion;
- physical fatigue;
- "automatic" performance of work (depersonalization).

Emotional burnout is a dynamic process that develops in stages. Ask yourself the following questions from time to time developed by the Mayo Clinic (Mayo Clinic, 2018).

- Is it difficult to concentrate?
- Is there insomnia?
- Are the results of the work unsatisfactory?
- Have you become cynical lately?
- Do you have to force yourself to do something?
- Is energy constantly at zero and you are unproductive?
- Do you enjoy food, alcohol or drugs?
- Are you annoyed, colleagues, students, people around?
- Do you have a headache, nausea, new health problems?

If you answered yes to at least one question. You need to stop, take a deep breath, think about yourself, do not procrastinate!

Recent studies indicate a direct link between the syndrome and the possibility of developing mental disorders and diseases in severe cases [2]. Analysis of literature sources indicates numerous factors, causes and motives that influence the formation and development

of this condition. From our point of view, significant and significant in its formation are: a significant reduction in funding and subsidies from the state and relevant ministries; inconsistency of working conditions and its payment, the Covid-19 pandemic. Interestingly, the target for burnout is primarily conscientious, highly qualified teachers. A special group are teachers of higher medical educational institutions, because their trigger system is a set of teaching qualities, professional and medical in clinical departments, and also includes work with foreign students, which requires additional skills and abilities. So, the question arises: what are the ways of prevention to prevent the syndrome, the formation of immunity to this condition? But before proposing these preventive ways and even initial antidepressant models, it is necessary to analyze the existing psycho-emotional background, its analytical model. This can be done by testing both independently and with the help of a qualified psychologist to identify the initial source of adverse events, the causes of the syndrome. For analytical understanding it is necessary to divide the positive and negative aspects of the work, there may be a third party "hesitation", which is also important for the diagnosis of the situation and psycho-emotional state. Moments of live communication with colleagues in this thematic area and trainings offered by specialists (workshops on group and individual programs, coaching). This is necessary in order to manage the stressful situation and the state it creates [3]. An important point is to understand that against the background of stress, its strength and duration, there are certain physiological changes. Psycho-emotional load leads to changes in nonspecific anti-infective protection (decrease in the number of polymorphonuclear lymphocytes and their reactivity to phagocytosis). In turn, severe emotional stress can provoke allergic and autoimmune diseases (systemic lupus erythematosus, multiple sclerosis, rheumatoid arthritis). Of course, if there is a violation of the hormonal background in the thyroid gland, pancreas, genitals, then stress is a factor that will exacerbate the negative consequences for the whole body [4, 5].

The purpose of the study is to substantiate the methods of prevention of the development of emotional burnout in teachers of theoretical departments of Bukovina State Medical University.

Material and methods. To achieve this goal, 36 teachers of theoretical departments of Bukovynian State Medical University, Chernivtsi were interviewed. The average age of respondents was 38.40 ± 1.95 years, the share of men - 16%, the share of women - 84%, the average length of service - 17.40 ± 2.13 years. The average working time during the day is 8.00 ± 0.26 hours. The method of diagnosing the level of emotional burnout was used for the research. Boyko [6]. The methodology consists of a questionnaire that includes 84 judgments. Interpretation of the results is carried out in three phases, each of which consists of four symptoms. The sum of scores was determined separately for each of the 12 symptoms and the sum of scores for each of the three phases of emotional burnout formation. It was believed that if the sum of points is less than 9, the symptom of the phase is unformed, if the sum of 10-15 points, the symptom is in the process of formation, and 16 or more

points - the symptom is formed. With a score of less than 36, this phase was assessed as unformed, with a score of 37-60 - in the formation stage and more than 60 points - as a formed phase of emotional burnout. The results of the study were analyzed using Statistica 7.0 StatSoft Inc. using parametric and nonparametric calculation methods.

Research results and their discussion. In a survey of 36 teachers of theoretical departments of Bukovinian State Medical University, symptoms of emotional burnout develop in 54% of teachers. The development of such symptoms as emotional and moral disorientation, which is manifested by the uncontrolled influence of mood on relationships with others and the development of indifference in communication with colleagues. There is also a symptom of expanding the sphere of saving emotions, which is characterized by emotional isolation, alienation, desire to curtail any communication and a symptom of reduced educational responsibilities, manifested in the desire to spend as little time as possible to perform professional duties [7, 8].

To prevent this syndrome, medical university teachers can use a variety of methods to harmonize mental and physical health, which can be divided into 3 groups: the impact on physical, emotional and impact on thoughts and worldview.

Increasing physical activity, improving blood circulation and functional state of the musculoskeletal system helps to release from the tissues and neutralize stress hormones, the increased concentration of which reduces stress resistance. Regular moderate physical activity improves the psycho-emotional state and functioning of the body [9].

To improve physical condition recommend: long and quality sleep, balanced, rich in vitamins and minerals (especially anti-stress minerals are magnesium and vitamins E and C, which are found in many fruits, corn, carrots, blackberries, nuts, sunflower seeds, soybeans), sufficient physical activity, sports, morning gymnastics, dancing. Positive effect has herbal medicine, homeopathy (mint tea, valerian root tincture, improves vitality tincture of Eleutherococcus, ginseng, Rhodiola rosea), massage, color therapy (green and blue soothes, red and yellow gives energy and vitality), aromatherapy (scents of lavender, anise, sage have a calming effect, help relieve nervous tension).

Normalizes emotional state: humor, laughter and positive emotions that have a stimulating effect on the immune system, activating blood T-lymphocytes, music, communication with family, friends, doing your favorite thing, pet your dog or cat more often (if you have one), hobbies and outdoor activities (books, movies, knitting, gardening, fishing), meditation, self-training (emotional stress is directly related to muscle tension – in a state of stress the body enters a state of "combat readiness", and by relieving the tension of a certain muscle group, you can influence negative emotions, get rid of them).

Changing worldviews, influencing thoughts also play an important role, try not to communicate with people who have betrayed or let you down, because resentment, anger, resentment, criticism of yourself and

others – all these are the most harmful emotions for our body. Give up the habit of constantly complaining. Find a place to stop work (toggle effect). It is proved that the influence of stress is a different activity of genetically determined stress systems and stress-limiting systems, but the interaction of which can change in the process of human life. Our brain releases stress hormones into any stimuli that threaten our peace. So, it is important to learn to control your thoughts and emotions, and remember: no one owes anyone anything [10, 11].

Conclusions. Scientific and pedagogical activity of teachers of higher educational medical institutions is characterized by a high level of emotional stress, resulting in a syndrome of "emotional burnout", which manifests itself in both physical and psychological fatigue, personality depersonalization, anxiety and depression with concurrent symptoms languages. Therefore, in order to prevent the development of symptoms of emotional burnout, teachers need to systematically monitor physical and mental health, and in case of signs of emotional burnout, you should optimize working conditions, normalize interpersonal relationships in the team and family. And the basis for the prevention of emotional burnout is: determining the time frame for achieving goals; use of time-outs; mastering the skills of self-regulation; professional development and self-improvement; avoid unnecessary competition; emotional communication outside of work; maintaining good physical shape; observance of the regime of the day; non-work-related parallel activities. And remember: "selflessness is a disability" the teacher has the right to free time!

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МЕТОДИКА ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫХ МОДУЛЕЙ В УЧЕБНОМ ПРОЦЕССЕ

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METHODS OF USING INTERACTIVE MODULES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Аннотация

В данной статье говорится о методике применения интерактивных моделей в учебном процессе, которые состоят из организационно-методических блоков, направленные на максимально быстрое и эффективное достижение какой – либо педагогической цели-передачи информации, выполнения практических упражнений, контроля знаний.

Abstract

This article talks about the methodology of applying interactive models in the educational process, which consist of organizational and methodological blocks aimed at achieving any pedagogical goal as quickly and effectively as possible -transmitting information, performing practical exercises, controlling knowledge.

Ключевые слова: интерактивность, модули, инфографика, Canva, образовательные модули.

Keywords: interactivity, modules, infographics, Canva, educational modules.

Развитие образования является неотъемлемой частью в развитии государства. В Законе Республики Казахстан «Об образовании» говорится, что «главная задача системы образования – создание необходимых условий для получения образования, внедрение новых технологий обучения, повышение интереса учащихся к обучению»[1].

За последние годы произошло коренное изменение роли и места персональных компьютеров и цифровых технологий в жизни общества. Без них уже невозможно представить современного человека. Всё шире используются информационные технологии и в образовательном процессе, что повышает эффективность обучения. Цифровые технологии стали неотъемлемой частью общества и оказывают влияние на процессы обучения и систему

образования в целом. Создание знаний для эффективности, качества и достижения результатов с помощью интерактивного модуля в учебном заведении для учащихся.

По сравнению с традиционными методами обучения в классе, интерактивное обучение является чрезвычайно мощным средством передачи вашей организационной подготовки. Но как это гарантирует, что персонал останется актуальным и заинтересованным в предмете в отсутствие взаимодействия учителя или учителя и ученика? Электронное обучение достигается за счет использования различных интерактивных технологий.

Интерактивность в интерактивном обучении можно определить как общение между учащимся и